

Study of a Biowaste-to-Biogas System for Clean Energy and Waste Management

Prepared by:

Engineer Abdullah Mohammed Rabea Al-Ammari

Email: Alammari.business@gmail.com

Phone: +971 56 919 3198

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Abstract

This project explores an innovative approach to managing food waste in Dubai by converting it into biogas, a clean and sustainable energy source. With over 8,000 tons of food waste produced daily in the city, the proposed solution aims to reduce environmental harm caused by methane emissions while offering a cost-effective alternative to fossil fuels. The project involves the design of a biodigester system capable of producing and storing biogas, with a targeted supply chain connecting hotels, farms, and labor camps. Financial modeling indicates significant profitability, while the use of pressure vessels ensures safe storage and distribution. The solution not only addresses waste management but also contributes to urban cleanliness, energy sustainability, and economic growth. This report presents the full design, financial feasibility, supply chain logistics, and stakeholder analysis, highlighting the practicality and scalability of the proposed biowaste-to-biogas conversion system.

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Introduction

Our challenge was present to convert biodegradable waste into energy efficient in city of Dubai. We were given a problem statement situation about on how Dubai generates around 8,000 ton of food waste per day methane produce in Dubai which is equivalent to 25 more times dangerous than carbon emission, so we were working on efficient way to use food waste convert into energy to reduce methane gases and reduce usage fossil fuel to reduce climate change.

Background Research

The single largest component of our everyday rubbish is food waste. Food decomposition not only takes up a lot of room in landfills, but it also releases methane, a powerful gas that traps heat in the atmosphere and warms the earth. That is why using biogas is seen as an ideal situation in the world since it uses the unwanted organic waste and use it as a source of energy with other benefits as well. Using biogas isn't limited to being used as an energy source, it will help our planet in many ways including cooking since biogas doesn't produce smoke, which is ideal for homes, this will save trees since firewood won't be required. The digested wasted material can be used as non-chemical fertilizers for farms and plants.

The process of turning food waste into biogas is similar to the digestive system of a cow. Bacteria in a cow's stomach converts the food that is eaten by the cow into dung and a mix of methane and carbon dioxide. The process of making biogas is similar but on a larger scale since large containers and gas cylinders are needed to hold the mixture of decomposing matter which is similar to a cow's stomach in the process of digestion. A container is used to gather all the biogas released from the gas cylinders and more organic waste is added into the cylinders afterwards. The containers must be stored in a temperature of 35°C which is ideal for a country such as the UAE since the gas cylinders don't need to be stored in special places.

Biodigesters are used to digest the food waste and turn it into biogas and semisolid material. Biodigesters can come in many designs the dome biodigester, tubular bag biodigester, or ARTI floating dome biodigester. Each design serves a purpose but use the same method to digest and produce biogas. Dome biodigesters are mostly used for providing gas to kitchen stoves due to the convenient design in the gas outlet. Tubular bag biodigesters are often used in a larger scale since the pipes that food waste flow in and out are large enough for large quantities and volumes and the process is very efficient.

Problem Statement

Our old problem statement was "What is the required time to produce enough friendly energy for powering charging station? ". However, since we have moved on to a more economical solution our new problem statement is "How do we efficiently produce, store and deliver biogas to our consumers"

Solution

A solution for reducing harmful gasses from cars and ex, is using renewable energy such as wind water and sun. and UAE has both sun energy, and it can be used as UAE is a desert area and also water energy.

Wastes can be recycled in many ways, so we reduce the rate of waste and rate of gasses formed from it. for example, recycling cans wastes. Also, when we make biogas popular than other gas this will make many areas healthy even in the rate of carbon and oxygen

- Giving hotels a data logging application, which will help us track the average daily waste.
 1. To help the hotels we use some points
 2. Using water filters instead of plastic bottles.
 3. Reducing and reusing supplies packaging materials.
 4. Reducing the number of paper products.

As the wastes are doing methane gas and its harmful so, you can reduce greenhouse gas emissions by doing the following:

1. Reduce your purchases of new items.
2. Teach your school the three R's.
3. Buy recycled.

Borrow or rent items that you will only need for a short period of time, and reuse what you already have. Also, these steps may reduce waste as well.

Project Design

Design process is one of the most challenging parts in this competition. There are many factors that should be taken in consideration before finalizing the design such as the emissions, heat generated and size of the prototype. We tried to make a small prototype of the actual process and adding an extra component which is known as the Peltier element. It is Thermoelectric cooling device which converts the heat into cooling condition. The prototype contains 3 inlets, two for the water and the third one for the waste and pumping oxygen in. It also contains two outlets for removing the water out. A gas cylinder will be used to generate the fire which will transform the waste in a gas, the burned material can be removed from the tank at the end of the process.

Water outlet

What is a pressure vessel?

It's a huge container that is designed to hold both liquid and gases at different pressure than surrounding air. These pressure vessel are used in variety application from industrial and private sector; and since these pressure vessel can cause failure in design due explosion there are usually followed with guidelines for pressure vessel design organizations such as ASME (American Society Mechanical Engineer) etc. some of these vessels are made of stainless steel however it depends on the application of the pressure vessel that uses on various conditions and resistant to corrosion material although some other steel alloy can be under vary condition as along the design of the vessel is follow on strict regulation according to acceptable performance for pressure vessel depend load bearing that can hold on pressure of the vessel without failure and prevent leaking.

Figure 4 Pressure Vessel

Figure 3 Engineering drawing from pressure vessel

Components of pressure vessel

1. Shell: - its forms as wall of the tank that holds both liquids and gases at acceptable pressure, and in manufacturing process it uses welding to form cylindrical and spherical and uses rollers to form shape and weld at each section made of stainless steel and other steel alloys, and sometimes it's with insulation

2. Head: - it forms end cap at end of the tank, and the head shapes comes with spherical and cylindrical uses welding technique to form it.

3. Nozzles: - it is a component that allows shell to connect with piping system to use fluid within shell, it comes with various fitting depend on consumer piping system.

4. Support: - it's allowed to form a base to hold on the weight of the pressure vessels and comes with various supports.

Figure 5 Method of Pressure vessel

Competitive Advantage

Our target market is hotels, labour camps and farms. We have an edge over other businesses as our market is also our suppliers for food waste, making for an efficient supply chain.

The benefits of our business model are that we buy trash from our target market, giving them monetary compensation, while also giving them a consistent supply of biogas that is clean and safe. Because we get rid of excess food waste, we maintain urban cleanliness and help in reducing pollution. This also means that the waste we convert to biogas is also put to good use, providing clean energy not reliant on fossil fuels.

We can buy trash for cheap, providing a low overhead cost for our business and incentivizing our consumers to properly categorize waste. In return, our consumers get a supply of biogas that is affordable and consistently available, which is a convenience.

The idea of converting food waste into biogas, storing it, and then delivering it to our consumers covers the issue of getting productive use of compost waste and storing alternative and clean energy. With storage tanks, we will have a backup supply of biogas and can also store it for long term.

Financial

Financial Modelling

The idea from the basic is to convert spent and wasted waste into energy through which all consumers can benefit from it, the idea is to convert waste through treatment into methane gas through pressure and some other factors, which can be stored in gas cylinders for the purpose of selling it to homes And restaurants, many agencies and consumers, to use it as thermal energy that

helps in cooking and in accomplishing many things related to thermal energy. In the following form, the most important statistics related to waste for the Emirate of Abu Dhabi from 2017 to 2019 are presented, such as the type of waste and the estimated cost of collecting it. All information obtained from reliable sources (Statistics Centre 2019), where no results related to the year 2020 have been issued.

Requirements	Database		
	2017	2018	2019
Year	2017	2018	2019
Non-hazardous waste (Tons)	9,477,037	9,803,432	10,979,476
Hazardous waste (Tons)	180,410	181,937	248,157
Total Waste (Tons)	9,657,447	9,985,369	11,227,633
Cost AED/Ton	70	80	90
Total Cost (AED)	676,021,290.00	798,829,520.00	1,010,486,970.00

Cost: (WRITER, 2018)

Statistics: (centre, 2020)

Table 1 Financial Modelling

Through the official figures and statistics available to us, we must develop reasonable assumptions for the expected future results within the next few years, and in this case the economic feasibility study for the year 2020 to 2024 was conducted to estimate the expected cost and expected results. Therefore, we made a simple calculation to find out the annual rate of waste in general. The following ratios were obtained:

AVG Rate of increase per year	Percentage
Non-hazardous waste (Tons)	7.72%
Hazardous waste (Tons)	18.62%

Table 2 AVG rate of biowaste per year

Through the following data, it is possible to calculate the expected results in the future, as shown in the following table:

Requirements	Assumption				
	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Year	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Non-hazardous waste (Tons)	11,827,109	12,740,180	13,723,741	14,783,235	15,924,524
Hazardous waste (Tons)	294,368.33	349,185.04	414,209.61	491,352.94	582,839.88
Total Waste (Tons)	12,121,477	13,089,365	14,137,951	15,274,588	16,507,364
Cost AED/Ton	100	110	120	130	140
Total Cost (AED)	1,212,147,733	1,439,830,154	1,696,554,073	1,985,696,432	2,311,030,943

Table 3 the expected total cost for the process

To make things simple, the data is presented in the following graphs:

graph 1 the expected total cost for the process

After knowing the estimated cost, we need to estimate the profit from the idea and from the project by estimating the sells and cost. to estimate that information, we know that One

Waste management in Abu Dhabi								
Requirements	Database			Assumption				
Year	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Total Waste (Tons)	9,657,447.00	9,985,369.00	11,227,633.00	12,121,477.33	13,089,365.04	14,137,950.61	15,274,587.94	16,507,363.88
Volume of Biogas produced (m3)	2,897,234,100.00	2,995,610,700.00	3,368,289,900.00	3,636,443,199.00	3,926,809,512.00	4,241,385,183.00	4,582,376,382.00	4,952,209,164.00
Volume of Methane gas produced (m3)	1,738,340,460.00	1,797,366,420.00	2,020,973,940.00	2,181,865,919.40	2,356,085,707.20	2,544,831,109.80	2,749,425,829.20	2,971,325,498.40
Mass of Methane (kg)	2,086,008,552.00	2,156,839,704.00	2,425,168,728.00	2,618,239,103.28	2,827,302,848.64	3,053,797,331.76	3,299,310,995.04	3,565,590,598.08
cost of extracting methane(36.75 AED/25KG)	3,067,266,974.86	3,171,417,100.76	3,565,968,097.65	3,849,858,777.46	4,157,266,108.64	4,490,303,596.62	4,851,306,887.11	5,242,844,415.42
SELL (140 AED/22kg)	13,274,599,876.36	13,725,343,570.91	15,432,891,905.45	16,661,521,566.33	17,991,927,218.62	19,433,255,747.56	20,995,615,422.98	22,690,121,987.78
profit (sell-cost of produce - cost of collecting (AED)	9,531,311,611.50	9,755,096,950.15	10,856,436,837.80	11,599,515,055.86	12,394,830,955.58	13,246,398,077.74	14,158,612,103.68	15,136,246,629.17

kilogram of kitchen waste, if well digested, yields 0.3m3 of biogas (Dublin, 2008), and the density of biogas about 1.2 kg/m3. Generally, biogas contains around 60% percent methane, 30% percent carbon dioxide.

Table 4 Waste management in Abu Dhabi

In 2024, we expect Abu Dhabi to gain around 15 billion AED as a pure profit from extracting methane from the general waste.

So, we conclude that if we follow the plan, we can get positive profit which is reasonable to start converting the idea into real life as a real business, and the statistics provided from Emirate of Abu Dhabi which has similar vision as Emirate of Dubai.

Graph 2 The final price per year

Supply Chain

Moving to the supply chain, the ideal way to think about it is by firstly asking fundamental questions: What is the product? Who needs it and how to design a process that delivers the product to the end consumers efficiently? Firstly, most food waste producers in the UAE in general and Dubai specifically had to be specified. According to the literature review and the interview conducted with a procurement manager in the RAK government, the main three food producers in the UAE are farms, hotels and labour camps. An article published by Arab News in 2021 states that 30% of the waste generated in the UAE is produced by the hospitality sector including hotels. Food waste will be collected from hotels, farms and labour camps through a specialized transportation company. To minimize transportation costs and reduce carbon emissions, collaborative transportation will be used; an expected downside of this choice is the increase in operation time resulting in time inefficiency. However, this is not a critical factor in our case since the process of food waste generation takes time and the collection stage is expected to happen once or twice a month only. Moreover, since we decided to have only three main targets (hotels, labour camps and farms), we will not face any shortages. Then, food waste will be moved to the production plant in which it undergoes a series of digestion, purification and upgrading processes

to result in pure biomethane gas stored in gas cylinders. By-products of this process include organic fertilizers that are crucial in agriculture. The plan is to sell fertilizers to farms at a reduced cost in exchange for their constant food

Figure 6 graph 1 the expected total cost for the process

waste supply. On the other hand, biomethane gas cylinders will be sold to labour camps and hotels in also reduced costs in exchange for their continuous waste supply. Throughout the process, our role is to collect food waste from these entities and convert it into energy. The entities will not worry about the process as they are not involved, and they will also benefit from the cost cut

associated with the guaranteed discounts. We as well will benefit from the financial profits affiliated with selling the cylinders and fertilizers. Finally, the community will benefit from the reduction in waste amounts and carbon emissions. However, the remaining question is how will the product be delivered to these consumers? The answer is simple. The same process of waste collection will be reversed in which cylinders and fertilizers will be delivered to the consumers from the production plant. The only difference is that collaborative transportation cannot be used in this case because time is a decisive factor for consumers. The best part of the whole process is how simple it is;

Figure 7 The stages following biomethane production

furthermore, the primary concern from the beginning was how to make the process simple, practical and realistic. **Fig.6** demonstrates the supply chain starting from food waste generation until reaching the end consumer whereas **Fig.7** presents the digestion process and the afterward stages.

Stakeholders

A stakeholder is an external party having an interest in a company that can affect or be affected by business of an organization (Fernando, 2021). Stakeholders are important as they can improve or hinder the operations of a business. For our operation, the stakeholders involved are governmental environmental agencies, non-governmental environmental agencies (NGOs), transportation companies, environmental companies (investors) and governmental regulatory agencies.

A stakeholder matrix is a visual diagram to help sort the stakeholders involved in a project. Usually, it categorizes stakeholders in terms of interest and power relative to the business; interest being the active involvement of a party while power being the influence they have on a business. These diagrams help in discerning which party to manage closely, keep informed or to do something in between (Larry 2000).

Figure 8 Stakeholder graph

Environmental agencies and regulatory agencies are both high interest and high power as they both are concerned with clean energy and safety and can pass down rules and shut down or give clearance to operations. NGOs have high interest but low power due to having no legislative backing while investors may be interested, they currently have no stake in the business except in the future. Transportation companies are low interest and low power as they are independent contractors that can be replaced.

Conclusion

This project has addressed one of the most pressing environmental challenges in urban centres like UAE cities managing the massive volume of food waste generated daily and transforming it into a sustainable energy source. By designing a system that efficiently collects, digests, stores, and distributes biogas, the team has presented a viable alternative to traditional fossil fuels. The proposed solution not only reduces harmful methane emissions but also promotes a circular economy by converting waste into energy and organic fertilizers. With careful financial planning, a well-thought-out su

pply chain, and active stakeholder engagement, this biowaste-to-biogas model demonstrates great potential for real-world application in the UAE and similar regions. The design's simplicity and scalability make it both practical and impactful.

Recommendations

1. **Pilot Implementation:** Conduct a small-scale pilot in collaboration with one hotel or labor camp to evaluate operational feasibility and efficiency of the biogas production process.
2. **Automation and Monitoring:** Integrate IoT-based monitoring systems to track waste input, gas output, and system efficiency in real time, improving transparency and performance.
3. **Government Partnerships:** Engage with municipal and environmental agencies to obtain support in terms of subsidies, policy backing, and regulatory clearance.
4. **Public Awareness Campaigns:** Launch awareness initiatives targeting hospitality and farming sectors to encourage participation and waste segregation at the source.
5. **Scalability Roadmap:** Develop a step-by-step expansion plan based on data from the pilot project, including logistic upgrades and facility scaling to meet growing demand.
6. **Research and Development:** Continue R&D to explore other complementary renewable sources and optimize the digestion process for higher methane yield and better cost-efficiency.

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البريد الإلكتروني
info@economy.ae

صندوق البريد
901

فاكس
009712626000

مركز الاتصال
8001222

وزارة الاقتصاد